

Quantifiable Tenderness: Examining Consent and Mutual Subjectivity in Yuri R18 Works

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Abstract:

This study employs “sexual consent (four levels)” and “subjectivity (binary)” as parallel axes of ethical assessment to conduct a comparative content analysis between the Yuri section and the general-audience (platform-labeled) popular ranking on a specific website. Results show clear differences between the two samples in both consent representation and subjectivity. In the Yuri sample (n = 60), works coded as “explicit consent” and “ambiguous, consent-leaning” account for 78.3%, works with subjectivity present account for 68.3%, and 41.7% of works meet both conditions (“consent + subjectivity”) and are therefore labeled “consent with mutual subjectivity.” By contrast, in the general-audience sample (n = 31), works coded as “ambiguous, resistance-leaning” and “explicit resistance” account for 41.9%, the absence of subjectivity reaches 83.9%, and the “consent with mutual subjectivity” type accounts for only 9.7% of the sample. Although the sampling frames differ, this comparison suggests that within the platform’s mainstream visibility pathway, general-audience works are more often framed through sexualized, coercive, or de-subjectifying scripts, whereas Yuri works are more likely to place emotional relationships, reciprocity, and boundaries at the center of sexual narratives.

Further cross-tabulation indicates that “subjectivity” is not independent of “sexual consent.” In the Yuri sample, the absence of subjectivity rarely occurs in works with explicit consent; instead, it is mainly concentrated in samples coded as ambiguous, consent-leaning and ambiguous resistance-leaning/explicit resistance: the lower the consent level, the more concentrated the negative judgments on subjectivity become. This pattern is even more pronounced in the general-audience popular ranking, where—even among works identified as “consent/consent-leaning”—the absence of subjectivity remains high, suggesting that such “consent” may more often serve low-context objectifying portrayals rather than stemming from reciprocal emotional negotiation.

The study also cautions that, although depictions of ambiguous, consent-leaning scenarios are common within East Asian cultural contexts, they are not entirely without ethical risk. There may be implicit narratives that romanticize coercion and render it less explicit; from the perspective of consent representation, this remains a gray area.

Introduction

Yuri is a subcultural branch within Japanese anime/manga culture. One of its antecedents can be traced to prewar Japan's "S" (S kankei) culture, which depicted intense emotional bonds between girls (Maser, 2015). In a media ecology often centered on a male viewpoint, Yuri is a notable exception: it foregrounds emotional ties between girls and young women. These ties may blend friendship, romance, admiration, and care, and need not be reduced to a single affective category; yet its orientation remains consistently toward relationships between women.

For Yuri audiences, Yuri is more than a mode of emotional expression. It removes a male-centered viewpoint and instead focuses on intimate relationships between women. Here, girls are no longer treated as objects to be dominated through the viewer's identification with a male character; rather, they are subjects who are understood and respected within same-gender intimacy. Importantly, Yuri's audience can to some extent be observed as not strongly biased toward any single gender—diverging from the common assumption that Yuri is either "male-oriented" or "female-oriented." For instance, in a 2017 interview, the editor-in-chief of the major Yuri magazine *Comic Yuri Hime* estimated the gender distribution of Yuri readers to be roughly 6:4, with the share of women readers continuing to rise (波多野, 2017). In a subsequent 2019 interview, they further noted that sales strategies no longer need to be planned around audience gender (柴田, 2019).

Taken together, these points suggest that Yuri, as a subculture distinct from conventional patterns, has gradually become less dependent on targeting a particular gender for influence. This in turn implies that its sources of visual pleasure may differ from male-oriented works that emphasize viewer identification. As many Yuri fans describe, what they find compelling is less a specific individual than a captivating intimate relationship—a form of attraction that is not constrained by the viewer's gender.

Whether in the female-centered relationships it constructs or in the relatively balanced gender distribution of its audience, Yuri may be understood as carrying substantial potential—more precisely, a form of resistance to the continuation of existing gender institutions within 2D (anime/manga) culture. Yet in contemporary scholarship, analyses of Yuri still tend to take the form of cultural studies or case analyses (e.g., Maser, 2015; Friedman, 2017), while sample-based survey research on Yuri content remains rare.

This means that we still lack proportion-based evidence that can verify, at scale, whether Yuri creation places greater emphasis on relationship depiction and on portraying both parties as mutually recognized subjects. Filling this gap is the aim of the present study.

Dōjinshi are derivatives of dōjin culture and, in contemporary usage, more often refer to

original or derivative works created by fans around anime and manga culture. They can be divided into general-audience and adult-oriented (R18) categories: here “general-audience” is a platform category label rather than a guarantee of all-ages suitability on this site, while adult-oriented works often include explicit depictions. This paper focuses on a sample-based investigation of how sexual consent and mutual subjectivity are depicted in Japanese Yuri dōjinshi, in order to examine the ethical qualities of Yuri creation in proportional terms.

Conceptual Definitions and Operationalization

First, sexual consent is a key factor in defining real-world sexual offenses and is the primary standard for ethical judgment in this study. Hickman & Muehlenhard (1999) define it as communication—verbal or nonverbal—of a freely given willingness to participate in sexual activity. A systematic literature review by Anyadike-Danes et al. (2024) synthesizes multiple studies and identifies four themes for evaluating sexual consent: loss of capacity, use of force, use of threats, and lack of voluntariness—criteria we adopt as references for our coding. The review also cautions that university students may rely more on implicit definitions of consent, such as treating consent as embedded in an established intimate relationship.

This implies that some groups may mistakenly treat intimate-relationship status as permission for sexual activity, and this cognition can also appear as narrative logic within texts—something that warrants careful attention. In this study, I treat depictions of an intimate relationship as a positive indicator when judging whether consent is expressed, but it should not be used as a decisive factor on its own.

Within many East Asian cultural contexts, expressions of sexual consent are often relatively implicit. Works may not depict explicit verbal consent such as “May we do this?” or “Can we start?”; instead, consent may be embedded within narrative and behavior—for example, stopping immediately when a partner feels uncomfortable, thereby signaling the priority of withdrawability. To better fit these cultural conventions, we code consent at the narrative/behavioral level when an intimate relationship is established and depictions of withdrawability/exit (i.e., the possibility of stopping or leaving) are present.

Based on the literature above, we define consent to sexual activity as the presence of willingness to participate. Drawing on prior work on East Asian cultural contexts and dōjin culture, we operationalize sexual consent into four coded types:

Explicit consent:

Verbal: the work contains an explicit verbal expression of consent.

Narrative/behavioral: an intimate relationship and behavioral depictions of withdrawability/exit (or equivalent cues) are both present. When the two conflict, behavioral depictions of

withdrawability/exit take priority as the primary criterion.

Ambiguous, consent-leaning: neither of the above explicit consent depictions is present, but no narrative coercion, bullying, or humiliation is observed, and no clear verbal or behavioral resistance is depicted. If the parties are explicitly established as being in an intimate relationship, this can be treated as corroborating evidence that stabilizes a consent-leaning judgment.

Ambiguous, resistance-leaning: no explicit consent depiction is present, while narrative cues such as coercion, humiliation, bullying, punishment, etc. appear, or relatively clear behavioral/verbal resistance is shown. However, the act also contains partial ambiguity or partial consent cues (e.g., resistance early on followed by a later shift). To avoid misclassifying compliance chosen under threat to personal safety as “consent,” when narrative bullying/humiliation and explicit behavioral/verbal resistance co-occur, the work is not coded at this level.

Explicit resistance: when narrative coercion/abuse and explicit behavioral/verbal resistance co-occur within the same work, it is coded at this level. When narrative coercion cues are absent, works in which the overall interaction displays clear behavioral/verbal resistance are also coded here. If a party lacks capacity, because valid consent cannot be established, the work is coded here by default.

However, sexual consent should not be the only standard for ethical evaluation. Sexual activity should ensure that both parties are informed, autonomous, and capable of making valid choices; it should also involve treating each other according to a standard of mutuality grounded in care and respect (Lamb et al., 2021), without infringing on the other’s rights even when participation is voluntary. This leads to our second axis, parallel to consent ethics: whether subjectivity is present.

The presence of subjectivity requires not only consent to the act, but also recognition of the other as a complete person with feelings, emotions, and boundaries. Operationally, we judge this by whether the character is dehumanized, degraded, or reduced to a tool/object serving a particular purpose. A typical manifestation is portraying or defining a character as a “machine” for someone’s use or for sex. Even if such a theme does not depict explicit non-consent, its ethical acceptability remains highly questionable. In this study, we adopt a red-flag trigger coding rule for subjectivity: if clear cues of instrumentalization/dehumanization/degradation appear in the text, subjectivity is coded as “No”; if no such cues are observed, it is coded as “Yes.” For example, if the narrative depicts (or gradually develops) an intimate relationship and there is no clear dehumanization (e.g., being treated as a “thing” or “toy”) or belittling of one party, we code the work as having subjectivity present.

When both sexual consent and subjectivity are satisfied, the work is considered ethically

acceptable under our criteria and is labeled as a “consent with mutual subjectivity” work. We report the proportion of this type in the overall sample, and we also compute separate proportions for consent expression and subjectivity presence as independent variables.

Research Site and Scope

For data collection, via the Google search engine we selected a free manga website that is mainstream in Chinese-language circles and focuses primarily on adult comics. To reduce platform-algorithm interference and amplification driven by non-Yuri audiences, and to keep the sample closer to the section’s baseline distribution, we sampled the Yuri section using the website’s default chronological (newest-to-oldest) ordering. We filtered out photo sets, AI-generated content, and non-adult content; for long serialized comics, we sampled the first chapter by default.

Research Process

In total, we examined 91 works ($n = 91$): 60 adult-oriented Yuri dōjinshi ($n = 60$) sampled from the Yuri section (newest-to-oldest), and a comparison group of 31 works ($n = 31$) sampled from the same website’s general-audience ranking list. It is worth noting that during sampling in the Yuri section, we also identified a number of non-H works. This implies that, in addition to the 60 adult-oriented dōjinshi, there exists a substantial number of all-ages dōjinshi (in a broader scan of 85 Yuri-section items, they accounted for about 41.2%). Although the website prioritizes adult content, nearly half of the Yuri ecosystem on the platform does not center on explicit depictions. By contrast, within the portion of the general-audience ranking list we captured, we did not find all-ages content. This, to some extent, reveals a tension between “regular” content and Yuri content in their preferences for sexual depiction.

This auxiliary scan is reported for context only and is not included in the analytic sample ($n = 91$).

All coding results were recorded in an Excel file, including each work’s URL, title, publication date, and type, to facilitate subsequent verification.

Results and Analysis

Within the 60-work Yuri-section sample, by type distribution, “short story; dōjinshi” appears most frequently at 51.7% (31/60), while “long-form; dōjinshi” appears least frequently at 1.7% (1/60). Publication dates are concentrated in 2024–2026 (95.0% in total), with 2025 accounting for the largest share (70.0%), broadly consistent with the website’s chronological ordering. For sexual consent, works coded as explicit consent account for 36.7% (22/60), and ambiguous, consent-leaning accounts for 41.7% (25/60), meaning 78.3% (47/60) of the sampled works tend

to present sexual activity in a “non-violent/non-coercive” narrative framing. For subjectivity, the proportion coded as “Yes” is 68.3% (41/60) and “No” is 31.7% (19/60), i.e., more than six in ten works show subjectivity present (no de-subjectifying red flags observed). Finally, 25 works meet both consent and subjectivity and are labeled “consent with mutual subjectivity,” accounting for 41.7% (25/60).

In the 31-work general-audience comparison sample, the combined share of ambiguous, resistance-leaning and explicit resistance reaches 41.9% (13/31), while explicit consent accounts for 16.1% (5/31). For subjectivity, works coded as subjectivity absent due to dehumanization/instrumentalization account for 83.9% (26/31), with only 16.1% (5/31) coded as subjectivity present. Works labeled “consent with mutual subjectivity” number 3, accounting for 9.7% (3/31).

Metric	Yuri (newest-to-oldest, n = 60)	General-audience (popular ranking, n = 31)
Explicit consent + ambiguous, consent-leaning	78.3%	58.1%
Ambiguous, resistance-leaning + explicit resistance	21.7%	41.9%
Subjectivity = present	68.3%	16.1%
Consent with mutual subjectivity	41.7%	9.7%

Although the sampling criteria differ, we can still observe that Yuri samples score substantially higher than general-audience samples on both sexual consent and subjectivity. In the Yuri sample, coercive narratives exist but appear at a lower proportion and are more marginal; in contrast, general-audience content—despite internal variety—is, along the platform’s mainstream visibility pathway, unexpectedly clustered around sexualized and sexually coercive narratives. This suggests that, relative to general-audience creation, Yuri creation may more readily place emotional relationships and reciprocity at the center of narration, such that explicit coercion/abuse scripts are not the majority (ambiguous, resistance-leaning accounts for 15% of the sample, while explicit resistance is only 6.7%).

Metric	Explicit consent (n = 22)	Ambiguous, consent-leaning (n = 25)	Ambiguous, resistance-leaning (n = 9)	Explicit resistance (n = 4)
Subjectivity =	100%	60.0%	44.4%	0%

present				
Subjectivity = absent	0%	40.0%	55.6%	100%

In addition, subjectivity is not fully independent of sexual consent. What we observe in the sample is that it captures a narrative structure that shifts in the same direction as deteriorating consent boundaries. When consent is depicted more positively and explicitly in Yuri creation, works are also more willing to portray both parties as mutually recognized subjects. Conversely, when consent boundaries are blurred or eroded, portrayals of subjectivity also worsen, concentrating as consent levels decline: the closer a work is to resistance-leaning/resistance, the more often subjectivity is coded as “No” (explicit resistance: 100% No; ambiguous, resistance-leaning: 55.6% No; ambiguous, consent-leaning still has 40% No; explicit consent is 100% Yes). The absence of subjectivity rarely appears in explicit-consent works and is mainly concentrated in works with unclear consent and resistance-leaning/resistance, suggesting that insufficient consent representation and instrumentalizing scripts often co-constitute the same power structure.

This pattern appears differently in the general-audience sample. Although we label it “general audience,” in practice many works are male-oriented and aimed at catering to male desire. If we set aside the near-half share of rape/coercion scripts, the remaining consent narratives are often still saturated with dehumanization of women. This is why subjectivity-present content accounts for only 16.1% in the general-audience sample—52.2 percentage points lower than in the Yuri sample.

One more point must be stated frankly: although narratives coded as consent or consent-leaning far outnumber resistance narratives in the Yuri sample, this does not mean there are no problems. Because our coding of ambiguous, consent-leaning relies on the absence of explicit coercion/violence cues and the absence of clear resistance, it can successfully filter out many non-consensual narratives, but it cannot detect implicit coercion that is romanticized or made less explicit—such as “default permission” achieved through relationship identity or narrative omission. Such writing may feel smooth in reading experience, but from the standpoint of consent representation it remains a gray area.

Conclusion

By examining ethical qualities in Yuri works, this study operationalizes “subjectivity” and “sexual consent”—moving them from abstract ethical judgments toward statistically describable textual features. Through a small-sample comparison with general-audience works, we show that, relative to general-audience works, Yuri works are more likely to unfold through mutuality,

respect, and understanding. This ethical quality includes explicit or implicit consent to sexual activity and respect for each other as individuals. These findings also echo prior cultural research on Yuri: Yuri may be a form of tenderness, yet it can carry a power capable of shaking culture.

References:

Maser, V. (2015). Beautiful and Innocent: Female Same-Sex Intimacy in the Japanese Yuri Genre (Doctoral dissertation, Universität Trier). <https://ubt.opus.hbz-nrw.de/frontdoor/index/index/docId/695>

柴田, 勝家. (2019, June 5). 『コミック百合姫』歴代編集長インタビュー (聞き手: 柴田勝家) . Hayakawa Books & Magazines
(β) . <https://www.hayakawabooks.com/n/n377845272272>

波多野, 公美. (2017, December 6). きっかけは『ゆるゆり』! ブレイクする「百合」の魅力
を専門誌編集長に聞いてみた. ダ・ヴィンチ Web. <https://ddnavi.com/article/d420470/a/>

Friedman, Erica. (2017). On defining "yuri". *Transformative Works and Cultures*. 24.
10.3983/twc.2017.0831.

Lamb, S., Gable, S. & de Ruyter, D. Mutuality in Sexual Relationships: a Standard of Ethical Sex?. *Ethic Theory Moral Prac* **24**, 271–284 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10677-020-10150-8>

Hickman, Susan & Muehlenhard, Charlene. (1999). "By the semi-mystical appearance of a condom": How young women and men communicate sexual consent in heterosexual situations. *Journal of Sex Research*. 36. 258-272. 10.1080/00224499909551996.

Anyadike-Danes, N., Reynolds, M., Armour, C., & Lagdon, S. (2024). Defining and Measuring Sexual Consent within the Context of University Students' Unwanted and Nonconsensual Sexual Experiences: A Systematic Literature Review. *Trauma, violence & abuse*, 25(1), 231–245. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380221147558>

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